

Blockchain-based Local Electricity Market Solution

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Abstract—The growth of renewable energy sources usage at the local level contributes to decentralizing the power and energy systems. Nowadays, there is an increment of residential consumers becoming prosumers able to consume their generation or sell it to the public grid to reduce the electricity bill. This great penetration of electricity compromises the proper functioning of the system. Local electricity markets (LEM) are market platforms aimed at electricity end-users to be able to negotiate and transact it between them, thus becoming active players in the system, being a possible solution to balance local systems. Different approaches for LEM design and implementation are proposed in the literature, usually based on community markets and peer-to-peer. Despite their value, these solutions' scalability is compromised as these are centralized solutions, and processing can become very heavy. In this sense, this work proposes a blockchain-based distributed and decentralized optimal solution for implementing LEM.

Index Terms—Blockchain, Local Electricity Market, Prosumer

I. INTRODUCTION

Financial and environmental concerns worldwide are promoting the integration of distributed generation (DG) based on renewable energy sources (RES) into distribution grids, aiming to reduce carbon emissions and improve the security and affordability of the power and energy systems (PES) [1]. The proliferation of renewable energy sources (RES) reshapes the power systems sector [2]. The installation costs of RES are dropping considerably (namely for wind and solar), leading to a significant increment in installed units. Typically, final consumers are seen as static players and are unconsidered when developing solutions.

Nowadays, there is an increment of residential consumers becoming prosumers able to consume their generation or sell it to the public grid to reduce the electricity bill. As a result of the decrease in the price of installing DERs, prosumers are installing and producing more electricity to generate more profits, compromising the proper functioning of the power grid [3], [4]. Consequently, grid regulators decreased the feed-in tariff paid to prosumers for exporting electricity to the grid as an immediate solution to balance the grid, lowering prosumers' profits [5]. One promising solution for prosumers to surpass this issue is participating in local electricity markets (LEM). LEMs are market platforms aimed at electricity end-users to negotiate

and transact electric energy among each other, thus becoming active players in the system [6].

Different approaches for LEM design and implementation are proposed in the literature, usually focusing on two large groups: i) the community-based markets and ii) the peer-to-peer (P2P) markets [7]. These two groups mainly differ regarding their goal. Community-based markets aim to find the best possible solution for energy trading among several community players in a centralized platform. P2P, in turn, is a decentralized platform where peers (consumers and prosumers) trade their surplus or demand flexibility bilaterally. In its essence, P2P suggests multi-bilateral agreements between peers. Several projects emerged in this context, exploring the use of blockchain technology [8]–[10]. By definition, a blockchain is an incorruptible digital ledger of economic transactions that can be programmed to record financial transactions or anything of value virtually [11].

The several proposals found in the literature confirm the value and applicability of LEMs [12]. However, these centralized solutions compromise their scalability due to the high computational processing needed. In this sense, this work proposes a distributed and decentralized optimal solution for the LEM's participation, using blockchain technology for secure and trustful transactions. To this end, the proposed solution considers day-ahead markets where each player (represented by a software agent) runs his optimization to determine the amount of energy to buy or sell in each period, sending the results to the local market operator (LMO). In turn, the operator validates the results of all participating players to ensure the proper functioning of the grid, solving possible constraints and issues. It is a two-step process where each player finds the best possible solution for himself. After authorization from the operator, players trade electricity with their neighbors.

The following section introduces relevant related work regarding blockchain and optimization approaches for LEM. Section III presents our proposed solution, including the description of the mathematical formulation for the players' optimization. A case study demonstrating the applicability of our proposal and its evaluation is described in section IV. Section V presents the final remarks and perspectives of future work.

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II. RELATED WORK

LEMs rely on smart grid (SG) architectures. SGs require a high security level due to their automation and remote access features [13]. Blockchain technology provides distributed ledgers where contract and transaction data are stored securely to protect them from such attacks. Blockchain technology provides distributed ledgers where contract and transaction data are stored securely to protect them from such attacks. The interactions between the various players are signed and encrypted with pairs of private and public keys [14]. The integrity and authorship of the data are ensured through the signatures if the keys are safely secured [15]. Moreover, blockchain technology is tamper-proof, i.e., data stays in a permanent state and cannot be modified [16]. Using blockchain allows automatic payments without human interaction. Such payments lean on conditions previously agreed by the stakeholders that, if met, trigger the automatic transaction [17]. These constraints are verified and ensured by smart contracts which are programable scripts stored in the blockchain.

Several works propose the use of blockchain in power and energy systems transactions. One of the most well-known examples is the Brooklyn Microgrid case study [9], demonstrating that blockchain is suitable for operating decentralized electricity markets in microgrids. The authors introduce a market design framework to evaluate the use of blockchain technology in P2P negotiations between households. Blockchain has proven its significance regarding communications, transactions, and security among stakeholders. Pieroni et al. [18] present another example of the use of blockchain within microgrids, proposing an innovative synergy applied in the scope of smart cities. Adding blockchain to microgrids allowed the implementation of a LEM between the actors that produce/consume energy. On the other hand, Li et al. [19] propose using blockchain for decentralized transactive energy management systems in networked microgrids. Their work presents a set of interoperable blockchains embedded with self-enforcing smart contracts to manage energy and financial flows among credibly transacting microgrids, suggesting additional smart contract measures to ensure trust and security within energy transactions. The authors conclude that employing blockchain in transactive energy systems will play a significant role in future power distribution systems. Noor et al. [20] present a non-cooperative game theory-based model for demand-side management between LEM players to optimize the balance between energy demand and generation while optimizing their profits. The authors used blockchain for transparent information exchange among peers, proving, through simulation, its applicability in real-world applications. Long et al. [21] propose a constrained non-linear programming optimization algorithm with a rolling horizon to minimize the electricity costs of participating players in a microgrid. Players share electric energy in P2P trading using blockchain. The proposed optimization reduces energy costs by 30% compared with traditional P2P. Petrović and Kocić [22] present a blockchain-based efficient energy trading within SGs. The blockchain technology supports a smart contract generator as the backbone of the presented system. The proposed system uses a deep learning load forecast model and a linear optimization model for optimal energy distribution.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

This work presents a distributed and decentralized optimal solution for the LEM participation, using blockchain technology for secure and trustful transactions. Optimal since this work proposes a two-step optimization model for the LEM participation. Decentralized means that the optimization model is not executed by a central entity managing the participating players to maximize the LEM's welfare. Instead, each player runs the proposed optimization model, competing with the remaining players. Distributed, in turn, refers to using blockchain technology and distributed ledgers for storing smart contracts after the market-clearing for safe and reliable transactions. The market-clearing resolution is for the day-ahead, considering a community-based market managed by a local operator. It means that the clearing price settlement is made centrally by the operator. However, each participating player (represented by a software agent) runs the proposed two-step optimization model. It is a mixed-integer linear optimization aiming to minimize the costs of market operation. Usually, this type of optimization is made centrally by the operator. Thus, our solution proposes decentralized optimization, where each player competes with the other participating players.

In the first step, the optimization model determines the player's amount of energy to trade ($P_{i,t}^{bLem}$ and $P_{i,t}^{sLem}$) in the LEM considering as price ($c_{i,t}^{Lem}$) the average between the feed-in tariff ($c_{i,t}^{SG}$) and the electricity tariff ($c_{i,t}^{bG}$) contracted with the retailer. Using the optimization results, the player sends his bids to the LMO determining the prices strategically. The LMO runs a double-sided auction market pool to determine the accepted and refused bids and the market-clearing price for each negotiation period. The LMO then instantiates a smart contract for each player with the market results for the next day. Listing 1 (see Appendix) presents a snippet of the smart contract. Using blockchain technology allows the automatic validation and acceptance of smart contracts while ensuring trust among stakeholders and data security and privacy.

After receiving the contract and results of the market-clearing, each player reruns the optimization model (step two) using the market price ($c_{i,t}^{Lem}$) determined in the LEM and the traded amount for each period to minimize the costs of the energy bought from the retailer ($c_{i,t}^{bG}$). The negotiated energy will be traded on the next day, and smart contracts ensure each player only pays or receives the amount of actual traded energy. The mathematical model of the optimization is presented next for prosumers, consumers, and LMO.

A. Prosumers model

Equation (1) presents the costs for the prosumers while considering the expenses of purchasing electricity from the grid and LEM and the profits of selling electricity to the grid and LEM.

$$Pro_i^{Costs} = \text{minimize} \sum_{t=1}^{N_t} \left(\begin{array}{c} (P_{i,t}^{bG} \times c_{i,t}^{bG} - P_{i,t}^{sG} \times c_{i,t}^{sG} + \\ (P_{i,t}^{bLem} - P_{i,t}^{sLem}) \times c_{i,t}^{Lem}) \times \\ \frac{1}{\Delta t} \end{array} \right) \quad (1)$$

where, Pro_i^{Costs} represents the operational costs of prosumer i , $P_{i,t}^{bG}$ represents the power purchased from the grid, $c_{i,t}^{bG}$ is the grid's electricity tariff, $P_{i,t}^{sG}$ is the power transferred to the grid, $c_{i,t}^{sG}$ is the grid's selling tariff, $P_{i,t}^{bLem}$ is the power purchased from the LEM, $P_{i,t}^{sLem}$ is the power sold to the LEM, $c_{i,t}^{Lem}$ is the price of electricity in the LEM, Δt is the factor used to change the negotiation periods' values to hourly values, t is the respective period and N_t is the total number of periods.

Equation (2) presents the energy balance equation.

$$P_{i,t}^{load} + P_{i,t}^{export} + P_{i,t}^{ch} = P_{i,t}^{gen} + P_{i,t}^{import} + P_{i,t}^{dch}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (2)$$

where, $P_{i,t}^{load}$ corresponds to the load value, $P_{i,t}^{export}$ is the exported power, $P_{i,t}^{ch}$ is the battery charge power, $P_{i,t}^{gen}$ is the power generated by the PV, $P_{i,t}^{import}$ corresponds to the imported power and $P_{i,t}^{dch}$ is the power discharged from the battery.

Equations (3) and (4) present the imported and exported power, respectively.

$$P_{i,t}^{import} = P_{i,t}^{bG} + P_{i,t}^{bLem}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (3)$$

$$P_{i,t}^{export} = P_{i,t}^{sG} + P_{i,t}^{sLem}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (4)$$

Equations (5) and (6) present the limits for importing and exporting power, respectively.

$$0 \leq P_{i,t}^{import} \leq \overline{P_i^{import}}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (5)$$

$$0 \leq P_{i,t}^{export} \leq \overline{P_i^{export}}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (6)$$

where, $\overline{P_i^{import}}$ represents the maximum limit for importing power and $\overline{P_i^{export}}$ represents the maximum limit for exporting power.

Equations (7) - (10) represent the linearization with binary variables for the buy and sell values in the respective markets.

$$P_{i,t}^{bG} \leq X_{i,t}^{bG} \times \overline{P_i^{import}}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (7)$$

$$P_{i,t}^{bLem} \leq X_{i,t}^{bLem} \times \overline{P_i^{import}}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (8)$$

$$P_{i,t}^{sG} \leq X_{i,t}^{sG} \times \overline{P_i^{export}}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (9)$$

$$P_{i,t}^{sLem} \leq X_{i,t}^{sLem} \times \overline{P_i^{export}}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (10)$$

where, $X_{i,t}^{bG}$ is a binary variable associated with the "buy from the grid" action, $X_{i,t}^{bLem}$ is the binary variable associated with the "buy from the LEM" action, $X_{i,t}^{sG}$ is the binary variable associated with the "sell to the grid" action, and $X_{i,t}^{sLem}$ is the binary variable associated with the "sell to the LEM" action.

Equations (11) - (14) are the constraints applied to control the simultaneous buying and selling in each market.

$$X_{i,t}^{bG} + X_{i,t}^{sG} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (11)$$

$$X_{i,t}^{bLem} + X_{i,t}^{sLem} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (12)$$

$$X_{i,t}^{sG} + X_{i,t}^{bLem} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (13)$$

$$X_{i,t}^{sLem} + X_{i,t}^{bG} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (14)$$

Equations (15) - (18) present the limits for the binary variables.

$$0 \leq X_{i,t}^{bG} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (15)$$

$$0 \leq X_{i,t}^{sG} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (16)$$

$$0 \leq X_{i,t}^{bLem} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (17)$$

$$0 \leq X_{i,t}^{sLem} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (18)$$

Equations (19) and (20) represent the state of charge of the batteries for the first and remaining periods, respectively.

$$E_{i,t}^{bat} = P_i^{bat\ init} + (P_{i,t}^{ch} - P_{i,t}^{dch}) \times \frac{1}{\Delta t}, \quad \forall t = 1 \quad (19)$$

$$E_{i,t}^{bat} = E_{i,t-1}^{bat} + (P_{i,t}^{ch} - P_{i,t}^{dch}) \times \frac{1}{\Delta t}, \quad \forall t \in \{2 : N_t\} \quad (20)$$

where, $E_{i,t}^{bat}$ represents the battery state of charge and $P_i^{bat\ init}$ is the initial state of the battery.

Equation (21) defines the limits for the state of charge level.

$$\underline{E_{i,t}^{bat}} \leq E_{i,t}^{bat} \leq \overline{E_{i,t}^{bat}}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (21)$$

where $\underline{E_{i,t}^{bat}}$ represents the minimum value for the battery state, and $\overline{E_{i,t}^{bat}}$ represents the maximum value for the battery state.

Equations (22) and (23) present the limits for the charge and discharge actions.

$$P_{i,t}^{ch} \leq X_{i,t}^{ch} \times \overline{P_{i,t}^{ch}}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (22)$$

$$P_{i,t}^{dch} \leq X_{i,t}^{dch} \times \overline{P_{i,t}^{dch}}, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (23)$$

where, $\overline{P_{i,t}^{ch}}$ represents the maximum value of the charge action, $\overline{P_{i,t}^{dch}}$ is the maximum value of the discharge action, $X_{i,t}^{ch}$ represents the binary variable for the charge action and $X_{i,t}^{dch}$ represents the binary variable for the discharge action.

Equation (24) is the constraint to control the simultaneous charge and discharge actions. Equations (25) and (26) present the limits for the binary variables.

$$X_{i,t}^{ch} + X_{i,t}^{dch} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (24)$$

$$0 \leq X_{i,t}^{ch} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (25)$$

$$0 \leq X_{i,t}^{dch} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in N_t \quad (26)$$

B. Consumer model

Equation (27) presents the consumers' costs of buying electricity from the grid and the LEM.

$$Con_j^{Costs} = \text{minimize} \sum_{t=1}^{N_t} \left(\begin{array}{c} (P_{j,t}^{bG} \times c_{j,t}^{bG} + \\ P_{j,t}^{bLem} \times c_{j,t}^{Lem}) \\ \times \frac{1}{\Delta t} \end{array} \right) \quad (27)$$

where, $P_{j,t}^{bG}$ represents the power purchased by consumer j from the grid, $c_{j,t}^{bG}$ is the cost of buying power from grid, $P_{j,t}^{bLem}$ is the

power purchased from the LEM and $c_{j,t}^{Lem}$ is the electricity tariff of the LEM.

Equation (28) presents the energy balance for consumers.

$$P_{j,t}^{load} + P_{j,t}^{ch} = P_{j,t}^{import} + P_{j,t}^{dch}, \forall t \in N_t \quad (28)$$

where, $P_{j,t}^{load}$ is the load value, $P_{j,t}^{ch}$ is the power charged by battery, $P_{j,t}^{import}$ the power imported and $P_{j,t}^{dch}$ the battery discharged power.

Equation (29) represent the imported power calculations, and equation (30) the limits for the imported power.

$$P_{j,t}^{import} = P_{j,t}^{bG} + P_{j,t}^{bLem}, \forall t \in N_t \quad (29)$$

$$0 \leq P_{j,t}^{import} \leq \overline{P_j^{import}}, \forall t \in N_t \quad (30)$$

where, $\overline{P_j^{import}}$ represents the import maximum power.

Equations (31) and (32) present the limits for buying power from grid and the LEM, respectively.

$$0 \leq P_{j,t}^{bG} \leq \overline{P_j^{import}}, \forall t \in N_t \quad (31)$$

$$0 \leq P_{j,t}^{bLem} \leq \overline{P_j^{import}}, \forall t \in N_t \quad (32)$$

The constraints (19) to (26) are applied for the consumers' batteries.

C. LMO model

The LMO is responsible for clearing the market, considering the buy and sell bids. To this end, the LMO uses a symmetric pool-based optimization method. Equation (33) represents the market-clearing function applied to clear the market.

$$\text{minimize } \sum_{b=1}^{N_b} (\lambda_b \times d_b) - \sum_{s=1}^{N_s} (\lambda_s \times S_s) \quad (33)$$

where λ_b is the buy bid price, d_b is the demand, λ_s is the sell bid price, S_s is the supply, N_b is the total number of buying bids and N_s is the total number of selling bids.

Equation (34), (35), and (36) are the constraints applied.

$$\sum_{b=1}^{N_b} d_b - \sum_{s=1}^{N_s} S_s = 0 \quad (34)$$

Equation (34) gives the perfect match between the total quantity bought and the total quantity sold.

$$0 \leq d_d \leq DE, \forall d \in N_b \quad (35)$$

$$0 \leq S_s \leq DS, \forall s \in N_s \quad (36)$$

where, DE is the total number of demand bids and DS is the total number of supply bids.

Maximizing equation (33), the demand and supply bids are accepted until both curves intersect, determining the total amount of traded energy. The clearing price is defined by the highest bid accepted in the LEM merit order mechanism.

IV. CASE STUDY

The present case study demonstrates the applicability of the proposed solution. It considers a local community of 20 prosumers with photovoltaic (PV) generation and energy storage systems (ESS). The minimum generation capacity is 1.5 kWh, the maximum is 7.5 kWh, and the total installed generation capacity is 105 kW at peak. The minimum and maximum capacities of the installed ESS are 8 kWh and 20 kWh, respectively, being a total installed storage capacity of 240 kWh. These prosumers participate in the day-ahead LEM to reduce their electricity bill and, at the same time, to profit from their local generation, registering their interest with the LMO. The LEM considers one operation day (24 hours) split into 15 min periods (96 periods). Figure 1 shows the average load and generation profiles forecasted for the next day in 24 hourly periods.

Figure 1. Average of forecasted load and generation profiles.

The total forecasted consumption is 887 kWh, while the sum of forecasted generation is 625 kWh. Each prosumer has a tri-hourly tariff contracted with a retailer. Tariffs may vary according to the contracted power of each player. Prosumers also receive a feed-in tariff for the energy injected into the power grid, which is equal for all and constant throughout the day. Figure 2 presents the prosumers' tri-hourly and feed-in tariffs.

Figure 2. Retailer and feed-in tariffs.

The feed-in tariff is 0.045 €/kWh, and the tri-hourly tariff is 0.0988 €/kWh in the off-peak hour, 0.1638 €/kWh in the peak hour, and 0.2278 €/kWh in the critical peak hours. Figure 3

illustrates the prosumers' contracted power clusters. There are five clusters among prosumers, each entangling a fixed cost. The higher the contracted power, the higher the cost.

Figure 3. Prosumers' contracted power.

Experiments were implemented in Python 3.9 with Anaconda distribution and Spyder IDE and conducted in a computer with an Intel Xeon(R) E5-2620v2@2.1 GHz processor with 16GB of RAM, running Windows 10. The software agents (i.e., LMO and prosumers) were developed using the SPADE¹ framework. Each prosumer runs its optimization. Although the optimization model is the same, each prosumer has its own knowledge and beliefs. The LEM participating agents have access to a private Ethereum blockchain. This way, smart contracts are kept in a distributed and decentralized Ethereum private blockchain and are resistant to failures and hacking. The smart contracts, developed in Solidity², are responsible for processing transactions, permitting only those that are feasible from the perspective of the energy transfers stipulated in them. Solidity is a high-level, object-oriented language for developing smart contracts.

As the simulation starts, each prosumer runs its optimization model (first iteration) to determine the amount of energy available to trade in each period of the next day (as previously detailed in section 3). With the demand and surplus determined by the optimization, each prosumer sets the demand/supply bids for each period and sends them to the LMO. Regarding the bid prices' definition, players define them strategically, considering the feed-in and retailer tariffs as lower and upper bounds, respectively. The LMO runs the day-ahead LEM determining the market price for each period of 15 minutes and the accepted and refused bids for each period. Figure 4 presents the LEM clearing prices for each period.

Analyzing the LEM's results, there were 73 negotiation periods where prosumers traded their surplus with each other. In the remaining periods, there was no clearing, and prosumers had to buy/sell their demand/surplus from/to the grid. The LEM average market price was 0.76 €/kWh. Figure 5 illustrates the sum of the transacted energy volume (demand and supply) per player.

Figure 4. LEM clearing prices for each negotiation period.

Figure 5. LEM transacted volume per participating player.

The LEM traded a total of 121 kWh. An average of 6 kWh per player and 0.25 kWh per hour (per player). Using the LEM results, the LMO instantiates and sends the smart contracts to each prosumer for acceptance. The contracts ensure the money transactions occur at the end of each 15 minutes-period of the next day to confirm the exact traded power. After receiving the LEM results, each prosumer runs the second iteration of its optimization model to minimize the cost of electricity bought from the grid. Finally, the total execution time was less than 35 seconds, which is an allowable time considering the use of the optimization model in a real-world application.

V. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a distributed and decentralized optimal solution for the LEM participation. Although the LEM clearing is centralized in the LMO, the optimization model runs decentralized in each player, making it a competitive game between participants who wish to minimize costs and, if possible, add some profits. Decentralizing the optimization improves the LEM scalability. Blockchain is used to sign and validate contracts and ensure reliable and secure transactions. In future work, the authors consider scaling the problem to 100+ players to see how the system behaves regarding execution time and LEM results.

¹ Homepage: <https://spade-mas.readthedocs.io/>.

² Homepage: <https://soliditylang.org/>.

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APPENDIX

Listing 1. Smart contract snippet.

```
pragma solidity >=0.7.0 <0.9.0;

contract DayAheadTradingSession {

    struct EnergyTransaction {
        uint period;
        int marketPrice;
        int energyToTrade; // > 0 if buy, < 0 if sell
        bool transaction_processed;
    }
    address marketOperator;
    address player;
    uint transaction_day_timestamp;

    mapping(uint => EnergyTransaction) public
    energyTransactions;

    constructor(address operator, address
    contractPlayer, EnergyTransaction[] memory
    transactions, uint timestamp) {
        marketOperator = operator;
        player = contractPlayer;
        transaction_day_timestamp = timestamp;
        for (uint i = 0; i < transactions.length; i++) {
            energyTransactions[i] = transactions[i];
        }
    }

    function trade(uint period) public {
        EnergyTransaction memory transaction =
        energyTransactions[period];

        if (msg.sender == marketOperator){
            int price = transaction.marketPrice *
            transaction.energyToTrade;
            price = price >= 0 ? price : -price;

            int playerBalance = int(player.balance);
            int marketOperatorBalance =
            int(marketOperator.balance);

            if (transaction.energyToTrade > 0 &&
            playerBalance > price){
```

```
        payable(marketOperator).transfer(uint(price));        }
        transaction.transaction_processed = true;            }
    } else if(transaction.energyToTrade < 0 &&                }
marketOperatorBalance > price){
    payable(player).transfer(uint(price));
    transaction.transaction_processed = true;
}
```

Authors' Version